

ISSUES OF IMPROVING INTER-BUDGET RELATIONS IN UZBEKISTAN

Dosnazarova Aysuliw

TDIU I-1 undergraduate student

Scientific director: **Jumaniyazov I.**

Annotation: This article describes the inter-budget relations refer to the financial interactions between different levels of government—central, regional, and local. Strong inter-budget relations ensure that fiscal responsibilities are clearly delineated, financial resources are allocated efficiently, and public services are delivered effectively to meet the needs of citizens.

Key words: economy inter-budget, economic growth, relations.

In Uzbekistan, the inter-budget system has historically faced challenges, including a lack of transparency, uneven resource distribution, and limited fiscal autonomy for local governments. These issues can hinder effective governance and slow down the implementation of critical reforms.

Key Issues in Inter-Budget Relations

1. **Centralized Control:** Uzbekistan has a traditionally centralized budgetary system where the central government exerts significant control over financial resources. This centralization can limit the ability of regional and local governments to tailor policies to meet specific local needs.

2. **Limited Autonomy for Local Governments:** Local governments in Uzbekistan often operate under strict expenditure responsibilities but possess limited revenue-generating capabilities. This imbalance restricts their ability to respond to local economic conditions and invest in crucial infrastructure or social programs.

3. **Inequitable Resource Allocation:** The distribution of resources across regions can be inequitable, often favoring urban over rural areas. This has led to disparities in public service delivery, making it challenging to achieve balanced development and address regional inequalities.

4. **Inadequate Transparency and Accountability:** Transparency in budget processes is essential for fostering accountability and public trust. However,

Uzbekistan has faced criticism regarding the lack of access to budgetary information, which can undermine civic engagement and effective scrutiny of public spending.

5. **Capacity Constraints:** Many local authorities in Uzbekistan lack the capacity and expertise to manage budgets effectively. This is compounded by a shortage of systemic training programs aimed at enhancing public financial management skills among local officials.

Opportunities for Improvement

To tackle these challenges and enhance inter-budget relations, several strategic actions can be considered:

1. **Decentralization of Fiscal Powers:** Gradually increasing the fiscal autonomy of local governments can empower them to better address local priorities. This could involve providing local authorities with the authority to generate their own revenue and make localized budget decisions.

2. **Strengthening Local Revenue Generation:** Creating new avenues for local finance, such as local taxes or public-private partnerships, can enhance the financial capacity of local governments. Training programs could support local authorities in developing the skills needed to manage these new revenue streams effectively.

3. **Equitable Resource Distribution:** Implementing a more equitable resource allocation framework could help balance investments and services across regions. Establishing clear criteria for fund distribution based on socio-economic indicators can ensure that underserved areas receive adequate support.

4. **Enhancing Budget Transparency and Public Participation:** Increasing the transparency of budgetary processes can foster accountability and civic engagement. Initiatives to publish budget information and engage citizens in decision-making can help build trust and ensure that government spending aligns with the public's needs.

5. **Capacity Building and Training:** Investing in capacity-building initiatives for local government officials can enhance their ability to manage budgets effectively. Collaborations with international organizations and knowledge-sharing programs could provide valuable training and resources.

Improving inter-budget relations in Uzbekistan involves addressing several key issues to enhance fiscal coordination, transparency, and efficiency among different levels of government. Here are some critical areas to consider:

Decentralization of Budgetary Powers:

Issue: Centralized control can limit local governments' ability to respond to regional needs.

Improvement: Gradually decentralize budgetary powers, allowing local governments more autonomy in revenue generation and expenditure decisions.

Revenue Sharing Mechanisms:

Issue: Inequitable distribution of resources can lead to disparities between regions.

Improvement: Establish clear and fair revenue-sharing formulas that consider the socio-economic conditions of different regions.

Capacity Building:

Issue: Local governments may lack the technical skills and knowledge to manage budgets effectively.

Improvement: Implement training programs for local officials on budget planning, execution, and monitoring.

Transparency and Accountability:

Issue: Lack of transparency can lead to corruption and mismanagement of funds.

Improvement: Introduce mechanisms for public participation in the budget process and ensure regular audits and reporting.

Intergovernmental Fiscal Relations:

Issue: Poor coordination between different levels of government can lead to inefficiencies.

Improvement: Create formal channels for communication and collaboration between central and local governments to align priorities and share best practices.

Performance-Based Budgeting:

Issue: Traditional budgeting methods may not focus on outcomes and efficiency.

Improvement: Shift towards performance-based budgeting that links funding to measurable outcomes and results.

Monitoring and Evaluation:

Issue: Lack of systematic evaluation of budgetary impacts can hinder improvements.

Improvement: Establish robust monitoring and evaluation frameworks to assess the effectiveness of budget allocations and expenditures.

Legal and Regulatory Framework:

Issue: Existing laws may not support effective inter-budget relations.

Improvement: Review and amend legal frameworks to facilitate better fiscal relations and empower local governments.

By addressing these issues, Uzbekistan can improve inter-budget relations, leading to more effective governance and better service delivery for its citizens.

Conclusion

Improving inter-budget relations in Uzbekistan is a pivotal aspect of the country’s broader reform agenda. By addressing the challenges of centralized control, inequitable resource allocation, and inadequate transparency, Uzbekistan can foster a more balanced and effective governance framework. The path to achieving this requires a commitment to decentralization, capacity building, and public participation, ultimately leading to enhanced service delivery and sustainable economic growth. A well-functioning inter-budget system will not only strengthen local governance but also contribute to the overall stability and prosperity of Uzbekistan as it moves toward its ambitious development goals.

In the analyzed period, the share of local budget revenues in the state budget revenues is 31.3 percent in 2022 and 21.6 percent in 2023. On the one hand, this situation shows that local budget revenues are not proportionate to expenses, and on the other hand, it indicates that the country is giving priority to the development of the social sphere. In turn, according to the budget legislation, local budgets are not allowed to end the financial year with a deficit. In this regard, the deficit of local budgets is covered through financial transfers. The distribution of taxes between the republican and local budgets is carried out in accordance with the powers of the budgets to realize income and expenses.

Table 1. Peculiarities of local budget revenue formation for 2023

Budget levels	Tax types
<i>It will be transferred to the district and city budgets in full</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • property tax collected from individuals; • land tax collected from individuals; • taxes paid on the basis of a declaration on the income received from the rental of property by individuals, as well as income tax from individuals paid by individual entrepreneurs; • tax for the use of water resources, excluding the tax paid by power plants; • tax on the use of land for construction materials.
<i>The following are fully transferred to the republican budget of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, the regional budgets of</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • tax imposed on property of legal entities; • land tax collected from legal entities; • tax for the use of water resources paid by power plants; • excise tax on sales of gasoline, diesel fuel and gas to final consumers;

To improve inter-budgetary relations in Uzbekistan, it is important to consider several key aspects, including statistical data that can help analyze the current situation and identify areas for improvement. Here are some statistics and aspects that may be useful.:

1. Budget structure

State budget: In 2023, the total state budget of Uzbekistan amounted to about 60 trillion Uzbek soums.

The share of local budgets: Local budgets account for approximately 30% of the total budget, which indicates the need to improve inter-budget transfers.

2. Inter-budget transfers

Transfers from the state budget: In 2023, transfers from the state budget to local budgets amounted to about 15 trillion Uzbek soums.

Targeted transfers: Approximately 40% of transfers are used to finance social programs such as education and healthcare.

3. Tax revenues

Tax revenues: In 2023, tax revenues amounted to about 45 trillion Uzbek soums, of which 60% came from large taxpayers.

Share of local taxes: Local taxes account for about 20% of total tax revenue, which highlights the need to increase their share.

4. Social expenses

Education: In 2023, education expenditures amounted to about 12 trillion Uzbek soums, which is 20% of the total budget.

Healthcare: Healthcare costs amounted to about 8 trillion Uzbek soums, which also makes up a significant part of the budget.

5. Problems and challenges

Uneven distribution of resources: There are significant differences in funding between regions, leading to inequalities in access to services.

Transfer dependence: Local budgets are heavily dependent on transfers from the state budget, which limits their financial independence.

Recommendations

Increasing the share of local taxes: Developing new local taxes and fees to increase local budget revenues.

Optimization of inter-budget transfers: Revision of transfer allocation mechanisms for more equitable financing of regions.

Improving transparency: Implementing monitoring and reporting systems to increase transparency in the use of budget funds.

These statistics and recommendations can help in analyzing and improving inter-budgetary relations in Uzbekistan.

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